

MOLECULAR DIAGNOSIS OF HUMAN PAPILLOMAVIRUS (HPV) GENOTYPES IN TEHRAN CITY

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Background and objective:

The human papilloma virus is known as one of the cause's anogenital cancers, including cervical cancer there is a strong link between presences of different types of human papilloma viruses to the development of genital lesions. HPV16 and HPV18 were defined as most important etiologic agents for cervical dysplasia and carcinoma. The aim of present research was to find genital HPV genome in patients with cervical cancer and control group and to investigate incidence of HPV16, HPV18, HPV31, HPV33, HPV45 and HPV51 types among patients admitted to medical centers.

Materials and Methods:

Fifty samples of women cervical paraffin-embedded tissue, HPV positive from pathology department of Imam Khomeini (RA) were collected. For this purpose, DNA was extracted and purified using a DNA Extraction Kit (Cinnagen, Tehran, Iran] from 50 patients with cervical cancer attending the Imam Khomaini Hospital (Tehran, Iran) and amplified by PCR. The nucleotide sequences were analyzed using the BLAST program (<http://www.ncbi.nlm.gov/BLAST>).

Results:

The molecular and pathological investigation of samples showed that% 71 of cases were HPV-positive. Out of them,% 41 of samples was determined HPV 16,% 28 HPV18,% 10 HPV31,% 5 HPV33,% 7 HPV45 and% 9 HPV51.

Conclusion:

As a matter of fact, the virus is not related to significantly detectable symptoms, and also the extreme prevalence of HPV in Iran, early detection of HPV can be prohibit preventing cancer development from precancer lesions. Therefore, using molecular techniques like PCR may contribute effectively to identifying HPV cases to diagnose in a proper time.

Keywords: human papilloma virus (HPV), cervical cancer, HPV genome, genital lesion.